

Brand Trust : A Differential Perception Analysis Across Income Categories Among Motor Cycle Owners

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Abstract : *Branding the product and attracting trusted customers are the most important elements in the contemporary marketing strategies. Consumers recollect the brands which provide them unique experiences and satisfaction. Brand Trust is the consumers' feeling of security, and their readiness to rely on a particular brand. This study examines the determinants of brand trust among owners of motor cycles and to analyze the influence of owners' income on various determinants of brand trust using well-structured questionnaire. Responses were collected of 120 motorcycle owners. An equal proportion of the sample respondents were drawn from each income class as per Mckinsey classification using non probability sampling namely convenience sampling method in Palakkad District of Kerala. The results derived from descriptive statistics indicate that the high income group or Global Indians have high degree of perception in Brand Expectation, Brand Confidence, Brand Experience, Brand satisfaction and Brand reliance, which influence the brand trust than other categories of customers; and the outcome of this could be generalized within the country.*

Keywords : Brand Trust, Motor Cycle Brands, Mckinsey Classification of Customers, Brand Expectation, Brand Satisfaction.

Introduction

Attaining brand trust among customers is an important strategy for business. Brand is the most powerful dimension that differentiates the products and services of one company from others which satisfy similar needs

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(Kotler *et al.*, 2013). A Company's brand name itself acting as a stimulus to induce the customers to purchase the product (Kaushal *et al.*, 2016). Customer perception of a brand's friendliness and integrity is the brand trust; based on the effectiveness of the products and the intensity of their expectations for the company, customers build confidence in a variety of brands (Coelho *et al.*, 2018). Trust creating a valid and important relationship to the brand and trusted customers are always loyal to their brand, ready to pay high price and they share product related information to others (Chaudhuri and Horlbrook, 2001). Customers must trust brands for them to be successful, and those who do so are more likely to succeed than those that do not (Portal *et al.*, 2019).

Customers provide a higher personal importance for the purchase of high involvement products, which involve a comparatively higher degree of risk (Dholakia, 2001; and Nayeem *et al.*, 2022). Companies that sell high-involvement products take the required steps to build customer brand awareness, brand trust, and product self-reputation. These internal selection criteria will have a significant impact on the buyer's intention to purchase (KIM *et al.*, 2020). Brand trust is significant in high involvement, premium product markets like automobiles and the stronger brand trust leads to increased purchase and loyalty to the brand (Sahin *et al.*, 2011).

Motor cycle markets are the most growing retail market; to attract customers and maintain long term relationship with them are the most essential elements in the contemporary customer oriented marketing. A number of makes and models are entering in to market day by day. Motor cycles are the most demanded forms of transport due to its affordability, easiness to operate and convenience to park. As these are high involvement product, customers are highly conscious about brand apart from the features and functional differentiation. Honda, Hero, Suzuki, Yamaha, TVS, Royal Enfield and Harley Davidson, are the commonly available brands in motor cycle market in India. Companies charging different prices for different models and try to positioning their brand in top of mind of customers.

Literature Review

Brand Trust

Brand Trust is the customers' sense of security towards a particular brand (Delgado and Munera, 2001; and Shin *et al.*, 2019). It indicates customers' degree of expectations about the performance of the brand; perceive the reliability of the brand and to recall while taking repurchase decision (Chaudhuri and

Horlbrook, 2001). There are two aspects or dimensions to brand trust. First one is the capacity of brands to meet its promises to customers and; the other dimension comprises of all attributes and intentions of the brand for keeping in mind the customers' interest and welfare. Hence a trust worthy brand is one which consistently keep its promises to customers through its product development, differentiation in production, sales, services and advertisements (Doney and Cannon, 1997; and Gansser *et al.*, 2021). The important further constructs for measuring brand trust are trust, reliability, honesty and safety (Chaudhuri and Horlbrook, 2001). Risk perception, service providers' consistency, sincerity, honesty and employees' fairness are elements of brand trust. (Adewale *et al.*, 2016). Brand trust influences the cognitive and emotional aspects of the customers, and leads to brand development (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Brand trust helps the customers to reduce difficulties to take purchase decision and the uncertainties of their feelings (Charton-Vachet and Lombart, 2018). Brand trust happens as a result of brand care, brand expectation, brand confidence, brand awareness, brand satisfaction, honesty, brand reliance, brand effort and compensation (Sahin *et al.*, 2011). Hence brand trust performs a crucial role in sustainable customer relationship. The Review of Literature explicitly brought out the factors influencing the brand trust of customers; namely Brand Expectation, Brand Confidence, Brand Experience, Brand satisfaction and Brand reliance; and which are used for the analysis in this study.

Brand Trust and Income

Income considered as the most typical demographic attribute for the segmentation of goods and service markets; and an important basis on which businesses target their market and offer products and services (Saad *et al.*, 2013). Socio economic variables are the generally used means for categorizing customers in to groups; Most of the marketing aspects namely need, desires, product preferences and brand preferences are highly related with these variables (Kotler *et al.*, 2013). Customers with higher income generally seek for quality products and are less prone to attraction by deals and sales promotion. But the low and middle income segments are attracted by various deals and offers (Dastidar, 2016). The income of buyers plays a moderating role between the emotional attachment and the brand trust (Atulkar, 2020).

Income of the consumer will definitely reflects their buying potential and consumption propensity. Income is the suitable basis for consumer classification of customers (Ramaswami and Namakumari, 2013). National Council of Applied Economic Research (NCAER) had introduced the first classification based on

income in the report "Income, Expenditure and Social Sector Indicators of Households in Rural and Urban India", 1998. By following this, Mckinsey Global Institute has also brought income based classification of Indian consumers; in their report "The Bird of Gold-The Rise of Indias' Consumer Market" (2007). Mckinsey classified the Indian households in to five economic classes on the basis of their annual disposable income, by making a minor variation in NCAER Classification (2007). They are :

- **Global Indians (above ₹10 lakhs) :** Senior corporate executives, huge business owners, elite professionals, politicians, and significant landowners in the agricultural sector make up this class. This class enjoys a very high quality of living and has truly global interests and preferences.
- **Strivers (₹ 5 lakh - 10 lakh) :** City traders, well established professionals, senior government officials, and wealthy farmers in rural areas make up this class. They are well-off in Indian society and have a steady source of income.
- **Seekers (₹ 2 lakh - 5 lakh) :** The people in this income class differed greatly in terms of work, attitudes, ages, and other traits. Newly hired employees, middle-level government officials, small- and medium-scale traders, and businessmen are included in this group.
- **Aspirers (₹ 90000 - 2lakh) :** This income class of consumers spends most of their income for basic necessities. This category comprises of small-scale business owners, independent farmers, and unskilled labourers.
- **Deprived (less than ₹ 90000) :** This class constitutes the BPL category. This is the poorest group.

Among these the middle class is made up of Strivers and Seekers. (Mckinsey Global Institute Report, 2007)

Brand Trust on Motor Cycles

The brand trusts of motor cycles were influenced by satisfaction, values, security and trust (Kustini, 2011). Customer engagement, customer experience and personal selling can increase brand trust among customers of motor cycles and the brand trust helps to develop repurchase intention (Ratnawati *et al.*, 2022). Brand experience has a significant role in the development of brand trust among motor cycle buyers. The satisfaction and level of confidence in the brand will

create a psychological impact on the customers and lead to brand trust (Saragib *et al.*, 2020). Brand personality increases brand awareness among motor cycle brands and it leads to brand trust; customer reviews and testimonials are also very helpful in building brand trust (Roger Seiler *et al.*, 2019).

In a country like India, with varied income categories of customers, it becomes imperative to study the relationship between the brand trust of customers of various income class with that of motorcycle brands bought by the customers.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are :

- To identify the most preferred motor cycle brands among the respondents;
- To analyze factors influencing the brand trust among motor cycle owners, and
- To examine the brand trust among owners of motor cycles across income categories.

Data and Methodology

The locale of study is the Palakkad District in Kerala. The study conducted between the period of October 2021 to September 2022. A non-probability sampling namely convenient sampling method was adopted to select sample respondents representing different classes of income as per Mckinsey classification. From each income class, 24 respondents owning motor cycles were selected resulting with the total sample size of 120 respondents. For this study, both primary and secondary data were used. For the purpose of gathering primary data, a structured questionnaire was created. Secondary data were obtained from published reports and journals. Percentage Analysis, Mean, Standard Deviation, Coefficient of variation and t test were applied to analyze the data.

The questionnaire used for the survey was designed on the basis of literature review. The questionnaire included three sections. The first section deals with the demographics of the respondents. The second section aimed to identify the brand of motor cycles owned by the respondents. The third section included the attributes on brand trust, prepared based on Sahin *et al.* (2011). The items were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale with agreement levels, ranging

from strongly disagree-1 to strongly agree-5. The reliability of Cronbach's alpha value was greater than 0.7, which proved reliability of the items to get the correct result (Griethuijsen *et al.*, 2015).

The demographic characteristics were analyzed on the basis of respondents' gender, age educational qualification and occupation; and the results are shown in Table-1.

Table-1 : Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	No. of Respondents (n=120)	Percentage
Gender	Male	98	82
	Female	22	18
Age (in years)	18-30	53	44
	31-40	31	26
	41-50	14	12
	Above 50	22	18
Education	School	39	32
	Graduate	38	32
	Post Graduate	43	36
Occupation	Government Employee	28	23
	Private Employee	42	35
	Business	50	42

Source : Primary Data

The sample respondents were aged above 18 years; 44 percent of them came preferably from the younger group of 18-30 years. Based on gender, 82 percent are male and only 18 percent are female two wheeler owners. 36% of respondents have postgraduate degrees. As regards to the occupation of the respondents, 35 percent of them are employed in private sectors, 42 percent doing their own businesses, and remaining 23 percent of the respondents are Government employees.

Table-6 : Brand Reliance and Brand Trust Across Income Class of Respondents

Income Class	Mean	SD	CV	t value	P value	H ₅
Global Indians	4.1	0.94340	0.23010	2.70031	0.01277	Supported
Strivers	3.2	0.87178	0.27243	-2.13542	0.04360	Supported
Seekers	3.5	1.02470	0.29277	-0.38247	0.70562	Not Supported
Aspirers	3.7	0.90000	0.24324	0.65320	0.52011	Not Supported
Deprived	3.4	1.28062	0.37665	-0.68858	0.49797	Not Supported

Source : Primary Data.

The motor cycle owners rely on their brand on the basis of their relationship with the brand owned by them. In the analysis the mean score of Global Indians is the highest with 4.1 and Aspirers scored 3.7. It is inferred that Global Indians have strong relationship with the brand of motor cycle currently owned by them. The hypotheses supported in the cases of two income classes Global Indians ($t=2.70031$, $p=.01277$ ($p<0.05$)), and Strivers ($t=-2.13542$, $p=.04360$ ($p<0.05$)) and there exist a significant influence of brand reliance on brand trust among these income classes of respondents.

Implications of the Study

Brand trust significantly varies according to the brand expectations of Global Indians. With the high income they prefer to spend to meet their expectations. The implementation of advanced technology, improvement of product performance and differentiation from other brands enhance the customer expectation and strengthen the trust towards the brand, while purchasing motor cycle.

The brand confidence significantly influences the brand trust among Global Indians and Aspirers. The customers whether belong to high income and low income category feel more confident on the brand, when they receive better experience from the brand, and keep promises which are relevant to them (Delgado and Munera, 2001). Transparency in business also increase confidence in customers. The companies should utilize social media platform to provide proper information and to post feedback of existing customers. Kaushal *et al.* (2016) also suggested that the marketers should be give adequate attention to

selecting the brand name and to endorsing their products through various mass media advertisement techniques. These will give confidence to the customers.

The brand experience is a key factor for determining the brand trust of Global Indians. Brand experiences create a platform for developing strong relationship among brand and customers. Brand experience arises in different situations; while search for the product, while shopping and while consuming the brand (Sahin *et al.*, 2011). Hence the automobile companies should provide unique and memorable experiences in their advertisement, and while offering pre and post purchase incentives and services.

There is significant influence of customer satisfaction on the brand trust of Global Indians. Satisfaction of customers can be achieved through better performance and emotional attachment. Chakkambath *et al.* (2022) identified functions and features as important factors to increase satisfaction of customers. To satisfy customers, the Company should focus on customers' needs and attitude, provide certain status and uniqueness and there by enhance the brand trust.

The brand reliance significantly influences the brand trust among Global Indians and Strivers, ie, both high and middle income groups of customers, who rely on a particular brand if they feel attachment to the brand. The companies should try to increase their credibility and reliability through attractive and trust worthy information system, through service quality and through efficient and trusted staff. Internal and external image of showroom and the courtesy of the sales personals play a magnificent role in customers for relying in a particular brand (Kumar and Narayanan, 2016).

Different groups of customers showing different levels of brand trust. Chakkambath *et al.* (2022) analysed a significant difference in the emotional states of customers among different categories of income. Hence the marketers of motor cycles should classify their consumers on the basis of their income, to adopt positioning strategies by understanding their expectations and try to increase the customers' attachment towards the brand. Customers are less inclined to switch brands when there is a high level of brand trust.

Conclusions

On the basis of the findings from the descriptive statistics, it is concluded that all customers are brand conscious and they exhibit a moderate level of brand trust irrespective of their income class, while purchasing motor cycle. But high income customers are showing a higher degree of brand trust, this will definitely

reflect in their repurchase intention. Hence creating brand contacts and building brand trust are the most important tasks of marketers to maintain long term and sustainable relationship with customers. The companies should try to market their high involvement products like motor cycle after categorizing the consumers on the basis of their disposable income.

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